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STUDY ON THE CAUSE FOR INCREASING ATTRITION RATE IN LOGISTICS SECTOR

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Abstract

An organisation's strength is its resource. Resource can be categorised into many segments among which human resource is the most valued and an essential element of an organisation. The paper is based on "increased attrition rate in Logistics sector". This paper would enable to understand the importance and the necessary of a company to retain its human resource which has become a serious issue in the current scenario. This paper intends to find the reasons for attrition and the measures to be taken by the organisation to retain its employees. Generally it has been seen that employees who work in organisations, expect the management to realise their full potential. In spite of this, there are situations when either the employers ask their employees to leave, or employees themselves leave the organisation. The problem of attrition of employees bothers both-the employer and the employees. Logistics has become one of the important activities in the modern era. Its contribution to other sectors specifically to the manufacturing sector is huge. Hence attrition in such a sector could adversely affect the logistics company itself as well the company who have outsourced the logistics to a logistics company. Measures taken by companies to preserve its human resource have gone to a greater proportion. At the same time employees attrition is unavoidable. This is a very big challenge for all the sectors of the economy. Analysts say that attrition rates vary between 20-40% in some organisations.

Key words: Logistics, Attrition Rate, Employees, Employer

Introduction

In the current global scenario, Supply Chain Management (specifically logistics) is emerging as one of the fastest growing fields of knowledge in this decade. Logistics is having the right thing at the right place. It includes planning, procurement, transportation, supply & maintenance. It can also be defined as planning, execution & control of movement / placement of goods / people & the related supporting activities within a system. Logistics deals with planning and control of material flow and information in organisations. It has become one of the important activities in the modern era. Its contribution to other sectors specifically to the manufacturing sector is huge.

Chennai, being a hub for marketing companies the importance of Logistics has shot up to a quiet high rate. It is either carried out in-house or outsourced. This led to the increase in the development of logistics sector. The importance of the logistics sector as such has

grown to a greater extent with the mutual increase in the number of manufacturing companies. Since the cost associated with transportation of goods and services is huge, it is often outsourced. This in turn led to an increased amount of logistics companies in our country. India spends nearly 13% of its GDP on logistics, as compared to an average of 10% in developing economies.

A reduction in the number of employees through retirement, resignation or death is called Attrition. Attrition is also called total turnover or wastage rate. This is natural in any business and industry. Causes of employee attrition can be as varied as human personalities, but some basic factors pervade most reasons for a resignation. While employees leave an employer for increased salary or career advancement, often the search for a new position is precipitated by dissatisfaction with an immediate manager. An employee's personality might not be a good fit for the job. New skills for an employee's current position could be needed. If the employee lacks the skill to do the job, the employee might resign. The rate of shrinkage in size or number of employees is known as Attrition rate. It is usually expressed in percentage.

Review of Literature

Employee turnover is one of the four primary dependent variables in Organizational Behavior (OB). This consistent with the view held by executives, HRD Manager, and researchers in OB that turnover has negative consequences for organizational performance. When employee quits and has to be replaced, the organization incurs some very real and tangible costs. The organization should retain their manpower for quite a long period. Attrition is a serious problem, that the organizations are facing today which affects their competitive advantage.

The tangible cost of employees' attrition would be the cost of training new employees, recruitment and selection costs, adjustment time, possible product and/or service quality problems, cost of agency workers/ temporary staff. The cost of training, cost of less productivity, cost of lost knowledge and cost of position remaining vacant till a suitable replacement is found. The intangible costs which may be even more significant than the tangibles, involve the effect of turnover on organizational culture, employee morale, social capital or organizational memory. All these costs would significantly take away profitability and competitive advantage of the firm. The organizational costs associated with turnover in terms of hiring, training and productivity loss. In today's competitive business environment, the impact of attrition on a business can be detrimental to both the bottom line and morale. Attrition can involve the loss of employees or the loss of customers. Both employee turnover and failure to retain customers over time can challenge managers. To decrease attrition, managers must understand the causes of customer and employee turnover, the costs associated with attrition, and finally, institute measures to reduce attrition rates. People leave causing others to work harder. They create a severe impact on the organisation.

Common Reasons for Quitting the Institutions:

- Inadequate Compensation Systems
- Inequitable Salary Distribution
- Different Rule for Different Employees and Favoritism
- Discrimination On The Basis Of Gender (Inequality of Treatment) That Cause Dissatisfaction
- Ineffective Role of Leader and Dictatorial control
- Poor Working Environment
- Poor Work Relationship
- Poor Career Planning and Development
- Higher Education
- Already Recruited In Corporate Sector
- Work Overload Organizational /Work Stress
- For Attractive Designation and Posts

- Lack of Interest
- Family Reasons
- Lack of Opportunity to Utilize and Display Talent
- By Mistake Falls In That Particular Job
- Incompatibility with Job Requirement
- Excessive paper work and working on holidays
- Lack of Autonomy

Methodology

Data was collected through primary as well as secondary data. Primary source was the exit interview forms filled by the employees leaving the organisation which were collected among 5 dominant logistic service providers in Chennai. The sample size of this study was 200. Simple random sampling technique was used to gather data from the respondents, because of which respondents diverged from every age group, gender, organization, marital status etc. The exit interview form was intricately designed to tap the demographic variables and also gathered information about the factors responsible for attrition. The data was collected from the employees leaving the company in the time frame April 2014 to September 2014.

The approach to the calculation of attrition rate might vary from organization to organization. While a few techniques are common, there are no proven theories.

These were the most commonly used formulae:

$$\frac{\text{Total Number of Resignations per month (Whether voluntary or forced)} \times 100}{(\text{Total Number of employees at the beginning of the month} + \text{total number of new joinees} - \text{total number of resignations})}$$

$$\frac{\text{Total Terminations in a month}}{(\text{Total Head Count at the beginning of the month}) + (\text{Total New Hires})}$$

$$\frac{\text{Total number of employee left}}{\text{Total number of employees at the beginning of the month}} \times 100$$

$$\frac{\text{Number of employee separations-involuntary separations} \times 100}{\text{*Average employee count}}$$

(*Avg. employee count = January month strength + December month strength)

Analysis and Interpretation

$$\text{Attrition rate} = \frac{\text{Total No .of employees left}}{\text{Total No .Of employees at the beginning of the month}} \times 100$$

Annual Attrition rate of staff level employees (April 2014- September 2014)

Month	Numbers	%
April – 14	334	56%
May – 14	407	65%
June – 14	358	56%
July – 14	394	62%
August – 14	428	66%

September – 14	384	60%
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Annual Attrition rate of executive level employees (April 2014- September 2014)

Month	Numbers	%
April – 14	18	32%
May – 14	24	42%
June – 14	26	39%
July – 14	18	27%
August – 14	18	25%
September – 14	34	40%

In the financial year 2014-2015 with respect to staff level, out of 7000+ employees, the number of employees who have left the organisation in the month of April is 56%, on May is 65%, on June is 56%, on July is 62%, August is 66%, September is 60%.

In the financial year 2014-2015 with respect to executive level, out of 800+ the number of employees who have left the organisation in the month of April is 32%, on May is 42%, on June is 39%, on July is 27%, August is 25%, September is 40%.

Exit interview form is issued to all the employees irrespective of their cadres (executive/ staff). The analysis part of this paper on “attrition” is done from the exit interview forms. It consists of all the demographic variables like name, employee code, date of joining, date of leaving, cadre, etc. the prime important aspect of attrition is the reason for attrition. Hence forth more exploration was done to find out the reason for the employees to leave the organisation through Exit Interview Forms. It includes

- Better Prospects
- Career Growth
- Family Problem
- Low Salary
- Medical Reasons
- Performance
- Personal
- Work environment

REASONS FOR ATTRITION

Row Label	Better Prospects	Career Growth	Family Problem	Low Salary	Medical Reasons	Others	Performance	Personal	Work environment
In percentage (%)									
Executive	8	6	4	1	0	2	0	0	0
Staff	39	22	45	6	25	30	4	5	2

Thus from the analysis made from the exit interview forms (sample size 200), it is clear that executives leave the organisation mainly for better prospects followed by career growth and then family problems. A better prospect is considered as the major reason for attrition at the executive cadre, whereas for staff cadre, family problem acts as a major hindrance triggering the employees to leave the organisation. The next important reason is better prospects as that of executive cadre. Medical reasons also play a role in the attrition of staff cadre employees.

In the tabular column “OTHERS” refers to other reasons for leaving the organisation apart from the reasons provided in the Exit Interview Forms. It includes higher education, conflicts with higher officials, Work Timings, Work Pressure, Inadequate Compensation Systems, Poor Career Planning and Development, Work Overload, Lack of Interest, Lack of Opportunity to Utilize and Display Talent and Lack of Autonomy.
 Suggestions and Conclusion

Findings

From the primary data collected through Exit Interview Forms an analysis is made on the attrition rate as well as on the reasons for attritions. It is found that 60% of staffs and 40% of executives have left the organisation with respect to September (2014). Henceforth attrition rate is higher in both cadres.

Reasons for attrition is analysed and is inferred from the Exit Interview Forms that In Executive Cadre, better prospect is one of the major reasons for attrition. Career growth and family problems takes the next position respectively.

In Staff Cadre, family problems play a vital role for them to leave the company and this is followed by better prospects and medical reasons respectively.

Suggestions

With the help of the data provided by the employees in the Exit Interview Forms I would like to suggest to consider these points and also to improvise on these criteria.

Attrition at executive level is a serious issue to be noticed, as vacancy at higher level of hierarchy would create management issues. For executive cadre better prospect is

considered as a major reason. In order to retain such higher cadre employees, stock options could be provided including a few promotion tools. Staff level attrition is greater in number. This leads to serious economic problems to the company as hiring & training involves huge cost. In order to retain staff level employees we need to consider the prime reasons for leaving the organisation. Family problems, better prospects and medical reasons are the major cause for the staffs to leave the organisation.

When we look at family problems, there are several reasons behind it like

- Location
- Bad health conditions of family members
- Transfer of spouse to some other location
- Educational benefits of children
- In order to retain employees who leave the organisation because of family problems, the company should
- Provide concession for the treatment of health problems in hospitals.
- Loan for employ's children for their higher studies.
- For better prospects as reason we need to consider some factors like
- Self-development
- To improve standard of living
- To improve knowledge and skills
- Higher studies
- Job enlargement
- Higher career opportunities (career advancement)
- Professional development
- Job security
- In order to retain employees who leave the organisation because of better prospects, the company should
- Provide proper rewards and recognition
- Improved compensation systems
- Opportunities for professional growth (promotions)
- In order to retain employees who leave the organisation because of medical reasons, the company should have a health centre in its campus so as to provide immediate medical aid to the employees.

Moreover the Exit Interview Form which the company issued to the employees leaving the organisation was not completely filled by the employees as it was difficult for the lower cadre employees (drivers). Hence forth I suggested a new Exit Interview Form to the organisation which could easily be filled in by the any employee leaving the organisation so that it would assist the analysis of attrition in a more effective manner.

Conclusion

Retaining the human resource in an organisation is very crucial in current scenario. "Attrition" should be given more importance not only because of the cost involved in hiring and training but also because of the talent pool which leaves the organisation. These factors will ensure its employees job security, job satisfaction, and will motivate them to put their full effort towards achieving the organisational goal.

Organizations should have a proactive retention strategy which helps in reducing employee turnover. Retention plan strategies should be different for different level of employees, because their roles are different; their needs are different; what motivates them are different and what makes them leave are also different. Based on the study it is clear that each and every organisation is keen to retain its employees as they value their employees as an asset to the organisation.

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